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Contents

Editors Note	5
A Study on the Separate Legal Identities of the Jains Dr. Anindya Bandyopadhyay	7
Śaivism in the Undivided Balasore District of Odisha Dr. Anil Kumar Acharya	19
Gender Taxonomy in Select Sanskrit Texts Dr. Priya Jose K	28
“The Tragic Fate of Katerina”- A Study Based on Alexander Ostrovsky’s ‘The Thunder Storm’ Dr. Jimly.P	39
Vedic Agriculture and its Implementation in Modern Farming: A Review Garima & Namita Joshi	46
Thematic and Psychological Aspects of the Curses in the light of the Mahābhārata- An Analysis. Pratiksha Goswami	57
Ṣoḍaśāṅgahṛdayam - Essentials of Ayurveda in a nutshell N Pooja, A Arhanth Kumar, K. Vidyalakshmi	73
Humanism in the <i>Bhagavadgītā</i> Dr. K.K. Abdul Majeed	80
Script, Language and Writing Technics of Manuscript Tradition in Kerala Dr. Manju P.M	90
Beyond Silence: Empowering Deaf and Hard of Hearing Students in English Language Learning through Multimodal Approaches Sherin Rahman, Dr R Jinu	96
Veda and the social life of women: A thorough study Dr. Moumita Bhattacharya	107
Ontological Conception of Anekantavada: The Realativistic Interpretation of Jainism Dr. Savithri.A	113
A Representation of Women Subjugation in K.R.Meera’s <i>Hang Woman</i> Meera A S, Dr R Jinu	120
Revisiting Law and Order in the rule of king Mattakala as depicted in Dasakumaracaritam Muthuselvi. A	132
Conservation and Management of Forests in The Hindu Vedas Neetu Joshi, Dr. Namita Joshi	137
Lord Rama as a communicator: Excerpts from Shriramcharitmanas Mayank Bharadwaj	144
Hospitality in the light of Indian culture and Sanskrit Sahitya Dr. Hemant Sharma	161
Exploring the Relationship between Translation and Social Behavior: An Investigation of Bible Translation in Malayalam Dr. Pratheesh Peter	172

Pūrva Mīmāṃsā Vs Śaṅkara's Advaita – A Reading of Śaṅkara's Gītā Upasaṃhāra Bhāṣya	Vishnupriya Srinivasan	177
Does Jaina Epistemology Indicate a Many-Valued Logic	Dr. Sabeena P S	185
जगन्मिथ्यात्वस्य चित्सुखप्रतिपादितं लक्षणम्	डा. सन्तोष .सि.आर्	193
महाभारते सूचिताः जीविकाः – एकमध्ययनम्	डा. के. रतीशः	199
अध्यासस्वरूपविचारः शारीरकमीमांसायां सिद्धान्तबिन्दौ च आशङ्कितविरोधपरिहारश्च	डा. अजिकुमार् पि. वि	203
व्युत्पत्तिवादोक्तदिशा कर्माख्यातार्थविचारः	डा. अजिमोन् सी. एस्	209
शब्दार्थचिह्नविनिर्माणे श्रीहर्षस्य कृतित्वम्	ड. साधन-कुमार-पालः	213
चट्टम्बिस्वामिनः दर्शने वेदान्तयोगदर्शनयोः समन्वयः	डा. आनन्द . एस् , डा. मिधुन्. पि	219
वैशेषिकदर्शने सन्निकर्षविचारः	डा. एस्. शिवकुमारः	225
धर्मशास्त्रदिशा शिक्षायां संस्कृतेः मुख्याङ्गत्वविमर्शः	डा. श्रीजित् टि. जि	230
श्री-अरविन्दस्य अद्वैतवेदान्ततत्त्वानुशीलनम्	डॉ. लक्ष्मीकान्तषडङ्गी	234
सद्योवर्षणम्	डा. ईश्वरः	238
विविधशास्त्रेषु प्रतिपादितस्य गुणतत्त्वस्य पर्यालोचनम्	रिया दत्ता	244
काव्यकारणविमर्शः	डा. कृष्णगोपाल पालः	251
मनुसंहितायां प्रतिफलितं सांख्यतत्त्वम्	लाल्टु रुइदास	257
पुरुषार्थानामुत्सनिरूपणम्	डा. वाणेश्वरजाना	262
आत्मस्वरूपम् – कठोपनिषदि श्रीमद्भगवद्गीतायां च	डा. बिन्दुश्री. के. एस्	269
स्वामिविवेकानन्दस्य जीवनमधिकृत्य प्रणीताधुनिकसंस्कारकृतकाव्यलयेषु सामाजिकमूल्यबोधः	डॉ. सुनीतावर्मन	272
मुख्योपनिषत्सु कर्मविचारः	मौलि एम्	278
रामरायकवेः अद्वैतान्यमतखण्डने जीवेश्वरस्वरूपविमर्शः	विजिता विजयन्. ए	281
वैदिकपरम्परासंरक्षणे श्रीमदनान्दतीर्थभगवत्पादाचार्याणां परमोच्चस्थानत्वम्	डॉ गुरुमध्वाचार्य तिरुमलाचार्य नवली	284
Concept of Ātman in Ayurveda and Tarkaśāstra	Dr. Devan E. M	287
Submission & Subscription		292

Pūrva Mīmāṃsā Vs Śaṅkara's Advaita – A Reading of Śaṅkara's Gītā Upasaṃhāra Bhāṣya

Vishnupriya Srinivasan¹

Abstract

The Bhagavad Gītā Bhāṣya of Śaṅkarācārya is one of his most popular works where he succinctly argues and establishes jñāna as the only means for mokṣa (liberation). In his *Upasaṃhāra Bhāṣya* – the concluding commentary, he raises all possible pūrvapakṣas against the siddhānta of Advaita Vedānta. This portion of the *Bhāṣya* is terse with arguments and counter arguments and is seemingly convoluted. In this essay, I aim to provide an exposition of Śaṅkara's arguments against the principal pūrvapakṣin², the *Pūrva Mīmāṃsaka* and show how Śaṅkara contends that jñāna alone is the means for mokṣa. I also attempt to show how he addresses the philosophical differences in the form of a debate with his imagined opponent (the pūrvapakṣin).

Keywords: dvaita, *Pūrva Mīmāṃsā*, *Bhagavad Gītā Bhāṣya*, Śaṅkarācārya

Introduction - The Pūrva Mīmāṃsā School

An understanding of the *Mīmāṃsā* school of thought is necessary to follow Śaṅkara's arguments. Dharma is the subject of inquiry in *Mīmāṃsā*. Jaimini defines dharma as a command or injunction which impels men to action. It is the supreme duty, the categorical imperative. The *Mīmāṃsā* view is that the entire Veda has karma or action as its purport³. Artha and Kāma which deal deal with

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 2. The commentary also deals with the views of other pūrvapakṣins such as those belonging to the Nyāya School
 3. āmnāyasyakriyārthatvāt ānarthakyam atadarthānām tasmādānityamityucyate - *Mīmāṃsā sūtra* 1-2-1

ordinary common morality are learnt by wordly intercourse but Dharma and Mokṣa which deal with true spirituality are revealed only by the Veda. The authoritativeness of the Veda is supported by social consciousness as well as by individual conscience. Dharma and adharma deal with happiness and pain to be enjoyed or suffered in the life beyond. Actions performed here produce an unseen potency (apūrva) in the soul of the agent which yields fruit when obstructions are removed and time becomes ripe for fructification. The apūrva is the link between the act and its fruit. It is the shakti in the act which leads to its fructification. Actions are first divided into three kinds – obligatory (which must be performed, for their violation results in sin, though their performance leads to no merit); optional (which may or may not be performed; their performance leads to merit, though their non-performance does not lead to sin); and prohibited (which must not be performed, for their performance leads to sin, though their non-performance does not lead to merit. Obligatory rites are of two kinds – those which must be performed daily (nitya) like daily prayers (sandhyāvandana) etc., and those which must be performed on specified occasions (naimittika). Optional rites are called kāmya and their performance leads to merit, e.g., he who wants to go to heaven should perform certain sacrifices (svargakāmo yajeta). Prohibited actions are called pratiṣiddha and their performance incurs sin and leads to hell. Then, there are expiatory acts (prāyashchitta) which are performed in order to ward off or at least mitigate the evil effect of the performed prohibited actions. The earlier Mīmāṃsaka believed only in dharma and their ideal was the attainment of heaven (svarga) but later Mīmāṃsakas believe in mokṣa and substitute the ideal of heaven by that of liberation (apavarga). Prabhākara and Kumārila⁴ both believe that the goal of human life is liberation, though both conceive it in a negative manner like the Nyāya Vaiśeṣika. The soul is chained to saṃsāra on account of its association with the body, the senses, the mind and the understanding. Through this association, the soul becomes a knower, an enjoyer and agent. This association is due to

4 The earliest work of this system is the Mīmāṃsā sūtra of Jaimini. Shabarasvāmin has written his great commentary on this work and his commentary has been explained by Prabhākara and Kumārila who differ from each other in certain important respects and form the two principal schools of Mīmāṃsā named after them.

karma which is the cause of bondage. When the cause is removed, the effect also ceases to exist. So abstention from karma automatically leads to the dissolution of the bondage of the soul with the body, the senses and the mind and consequently to the return of the soul to its pure nature as a substance rid of all qualities and modes including consciousness and bliss also. It is a state of freedom from all pain and desire and consciousness, though Kumārila adds that the soul is here characterized by potential consciousness. Prabhākara and Kumārila both admit that the abstention from karma does not mean abstention from all karmas, but abstention from the optional (kāmya) and the prohibited (pratiśiddha) kinds of karma only. The performance of the former leads to merit and to heaven, while that of the latter to demerit. The seeker for liberation has to rise above both merit and demerit, above both heaven and hell. But even he should perform the obligatory (nitya and naimittika) actions enjoined by the Veda. Prabhākara believes in duty for duty's sake. Obedience to the Veda is an end in itself and is of ultimate value (puruṣārtha). These actions must be performed in an absolutely detached manner without any consideration of reward simply because they are the commands of the Veda. Kumārila believes in psychological hedonism [3] and makes the performance of these actions a means to realize the ultimate end, i.e., liberation, by overcoming past sin and by avoiding future sin which would otherwise surely result from their neglect. Prabhākara believes in the utter supremacy of action, though he admits knowledge also as a means of liberation. Kumārila believes in a harmonious combination of knowledge and action as a means to liberation. He admits that upāsanā or meditation which is a kind of action leads to knowledge which ultimately leads to liberation. Kumārila's view of the self as potential consciousness, his emphasis that action is not an end in itself but only a means to obtain liberation, his acceptance of the view that knowledge of the self-born of true meditative act is the immediate cause of liberation – all go to make him a veritable link between Prabhākara and Śāṅkara.

The view of Śāṅkara

To quote Dr. S. Radhakrishnan, "It is impossible to read Śāṅkara's writings, packed as they are with serious and subtle thinking, without being conscious that one is in contact with a mind of a very fine penetration and profound spirituality... His philosophy stands

forth complete, needing neither a before nor an after... whether we agree or disagree, the penetrating light of his mind never leaves us where we were". Ultimate reality, according to Śaṅkara, Ātman or Brahman which is Pure Consciousness (jñāna svarūpa) which is devoid of all attributes and all categories of the intellect. The central thesis of Śaṅkara against the claim of karma serving as the means to mokṣa (either by itself or along with jñāna) is that karma and jñāna are both paraspara viruddha – opposites like light and darkness. The very idea of performance of karma involves various divisions, called bheda pratyaya⁵ in śāstraic parlance. Jñāna on the contrary puts an end to all such notions of duality and hence these two cannot coexist. In his commentary, Śaṅkara offers his defense against the Mīmāṃsā theory at two levels. First, he quotes extensively from Sruti, smṛti, purāna and itihāsa to establish the Advaitic standpoint of jñāna alone being the cause of mokṣa. Then he goes on to identify logical discrepancies in the Mīmāṃsā worldview. In this essay, we will only examine the latter.

The case of nitya and naimittika karmas

Performance of nitya karma cannot exhaust all pāpa

The Mīmāṃsaka too agrees with the Advaitic viewpoint that all karmas both puṇya and pāpa have to be exhausted in order to accomplish mokṣa. Śaṅkara argues that this cannot be achieved by the performance of obligatory rites as put forth by the pūrvapakṣin. Even if it can be agreed that nitya karma exhausts all of the previous pāpas, sañcita⁶ puṇya cannot be exhausted, which will precipitate future births. Also, the possibility of exhaustion of all pāpas through nitya karma itself is not tenable because it is logically inconsistent to claim that a particular number of nitya karmas performed in this birth

5 Śaṅkara enumerates the possible divisions that may be involved in an action. In any action there is the action itself, kriyā, the things connected to the action, kāraka and the result of the action, phala. The action is the basis for all the karakas. The first kāraka denotes the one who performs the action, the agent. What does he do? That tells us the second kāraka and if we ask how he does it, which gives us the third. For what purpose he does it gives us another, the fourth, and from where he does the action, gives us the fifth. Finally, where the action was done gives us the seventh. The sixth relationship is not a kāraka because it is not involved in the action itself. It is a nominal connection, and therefore, Śaṅkara mentions it separately, as the result, phala. When all these are seen as separate, it is called bheda-buddhi.

6 This refers to the sum total of all the paṣṭ karmas acquired in the paṣṭ lives. It is one of the three kinds of karma.

may neutralize pāpas done over many lifetimes.

At this juncture, Śāṅkara puts forth a convincing psychological reason for why one cannot avoid kāmya karma and niṣiddha karma altogether. The very motivation for the performance of niṣiddha karma in spite of knowing it to be niṣiddha is rāga (attachment) and dveṣa (aversion). Mere intellectual knowledge about niṣiddha karmas doesn't stop one from performing the same. As long as there is rāga and dveṣa, one cannot completely avoid kāmya karmas and niṣiddha karmas. Hence, the only way one can possibly avoid kāmya karma and niṣiddha karma is through complete removal of all rāga and dveṣa. The Advaitic proposition is that all desires arise due to inadequacies and it is only the knowledge that "I am infinite" can lead to the cessation of all desires. Hence, the Mīmāṃsā idea though theoretically feasible stands negated from the practical viewpoint.

Every karma has a result (phala) associated with it

At this stage, the pūrvapakṣin argues that nitya karmas do not have any phala and the very effort involved in doing them may be considered as their result. They are also ordained for different varnas as karmas that can be performed for livelihood. Śāṅkara invalidates their claim because if we were to accept that the very effort of doing nitya karma was a result of previous wrong doings, then there would be no explanation for other types of painful experiences one goes through in life. Also, one cannot claim that the different types of pāpa one might have performed in previous life will yield one particular type of pain – in the form of observance of nitya karmas. Śāṅkara further points that nitya and naimittika karmas lead to punya because Sastras have ordained them exactly like kāmya karmas⁷. Using the opponent's own argument, Śāṅkara corners him by stating that if nitya karmas have their result as exhaustion of pāpa but kāmya karma produce a different result, like svarga, there should be a difference in the itikartavyata (way of doing) and pain involved in both actions. But it is not so. Both nitya agnihotra and kāmya agnihotra have the same pain involved and hence cannot claim to produce different results. Thus, nitya karma has to produce a result and the result must be adṛṣṭa. Śāṅkara thus wards off the confusion and refutes the original argument of the

7 For example, there is no difference in the procedures mentioned for nitya agnihotra and kāmya agnihotra.

Mīmāṃsaka that nitya karma has no phala but has a dosa when not done.

Karma is preceded by avidyā (ignorance)

Through the course of his commentary, Śāṅkara brings forth one possible interpretation of the term ‘avidyā’ by the opponent school. The opponent claims that the knowledge of the self as being distinct from the body is necessary for the performance of any type karma ordained by the Vedas. This is because the fruit of all the karmas enjoined are adrṣta⁸ and are to be experienced after the fall of the body by the transmigrating self. In that case, the proposition that karmas are preceded by avidyā, ignorance of the knowledge of the self is false.

Any karma necessarily requires the doer to have this notion “I am the doer of this karma”, “I shall enjoy the fruits of the karma” etc. This notion is what we mean by avidya, Śāṅkara clarifies. Mere understanding of body being distinct from the ātman cannot be accepted as lack of avidyā. The philosophy of Advaita through the times after Śāṅkara has faced severe criticism from its rival schools of thought regarding the concept of avidyā. While post Śāṅkara scholars have struggled with the ontological status or modalities of avidyā, whether it was real or unreal, its relation to brahman, and so on [2], Śāṅkara has explained the process of avidyā using examples from ordinary life such as superimposition between a man and a post, a rope and a snake, and so on. However, in the examples he provides, an external knower jñātr confuses between two knowables jñeya. On the other hand, avidyā is the superimposition between the ātman as knower and the anātman as the knowable⁹.

Śāṅkara’s point is that just as the former superimpositions do not involve a real exchange of dharmas between the objects confused for each other, the same would be true of latter one. He offers the argument that the self being acala and any karma¹⁰ being

8 A pramāṇa is considered valid only if the knowledge produced through it cannot be known through any other means of knowledge. Hence, Saṣtra is a pramāṇa only with respect to those matters that cannot be known through other means of knowledge such as perception, inference, etc.

9 sthā nupurud sau jneyāveva santau jnātrā anyonyasminn adhyastau avidyayā dehātmanos tu jneyajñātror evetaretarādhyāsa iti na samo drstānta

10 Any karma - whether it is enjoined by the Veda, enjoined by smṛti or it is done as an atonement or it is a prohibition or it is in the form of a mandate or it is in the form of an option to fulfill a desire or it is purely a secular action, is done physically, orally or purely

calanātmaka, the self appears to be the doer because of avidyā and is akarta in reality.

“I sense” – Figurative (Gauna) Vs Erroneous (Mithyā)

cepting the idea of Śāṅkara's superimposition, the pūrvapakṣin contends that this superimposition is only figurative and not erroneous. In my view, Śāṅkara's elaborate analysis of the differences between “gauṇa pratyaya” and “mithyā pratyaya” are a joy to read. Here, the examples chosen by him to elucidate his stance are simple and popular everyday expressions. His ability to meticulously derive out of them conclusions that strengthen his siddhānta is a crucial skill that I admire in him.

Śāṅkara introduces two types of gauṇa expressions, namely, vyakta upamā and lupta upamā. He argues that the object of the gauṇa expression cannot do exactly what its object of comparison can do whereas in case of mithyā pratyaya it is not so. When one says, “I am the doer of a particular action”, he means it. The ātma is taken to be the doer in this case¹¹. A gauṇa is only meant to praise or reveal a quality of the thing being compared. It is not meant to be used to reveal a thing directly. Also, the one who hears this gauṇa expression knows the object described very well. There is no mistake, and there is, on the other hand, discrimination, viveka. Where there is lack of discrimination, and because of that, the cognition of a given thing in something that it is not (atasmin tadbuddhi), there is mithyā-pratyaya.

Uselessness of Śāstras

The pūrvapakṣin now fears that if the notion of agency is mithyā, then the entire corpus of śruti literature becomes meaningless as the injunctions in the śruti are all addressed to a karta (doer). It is here that Śāṅkara puts forth his revolutionary view that the śāstra indeed has no utility from the viewpoint of a brahmajñāni, the one who has realized the self for he has nothing to accomplish. But, Śāṅkara doesn't discard the śāstras as useless but treats them as distinctive sources of valid knowledge simply because they seek to make the unknown known. The scriptures have no validity in the realm of

mentally it implies some kind of motion. Hence, karma is referred as calanātmaka.

11 Śāṅkara says to the opponent, “If you do not accept that, what you are saying is what Vedānta says. If you know that you are not doing anything in spite of the body and mind's doing various things, you understand the purport of Vedānta. But if you claim that the action of the body figuratively denotes the actions of ātman it is not tenable

things that are already known to us through some other pramāṇa, means of knowledge¹². Śaṅkara argues that one doesn't need the śāstra to tell that one is an agent (karta). Further, if the notion of agency of the doer is dismissed as erroneous, the Veda ceases to be a pramāṇa only in the realm of karma and still holds good in the realm of jñāna. In fact, Śaṅkara upholds the supremacy of śruti pramāṇa by stating that there is no other means than the jñāna kānda to realize the self. The śruti is the only means here. However, he also establishes that the karma kānda does have its own sphere of validity. It can be used by a seeker for the attainment of cittasuddhi, preparation of his mind for jñāna or that it is valid for those who have the I cognition in the body mind complex and are interested in accomplishing the limited ends mentioned thereof.

Conclusion

In the *Bhagavad Gītā* commentary, we find that Śaṅkara has commented quite elaborately in some places, using them as an opportunity to expound his philosophy. He has adeptly used the context of Upasamhāra to critically examine his theory of jñāna yoga being the ultimate purport of the Gītā. He responds to all allegations raised by the Mimāṃsaka against non-performance of rituals mandated by the Vedas. He also rebuffs the repercussions this has for the meaningfulness of the śāstras by restricting their utility to unenlightened people who are desirous of the fruits realized from karma. Thus, through his commentary, he establishes the futility of karma as a means of liberation from saṃsāra which he attributes as the fundamental teaching of the *Gītā* in his introductory commentary.

References

- Warrie, A.G. Krishna r. 1983 Bhagavad Gita, Madras Sri Ramakrishna Math
- Kaplan, S. 2007 Vidya and Avidya: Simultaneous or coterminous? A holographic model to illuminate the Advaita Debate, *Philosophy East and West*, Vol 57, No 2 (Apr 2007), pp. 178-203
- Sharma, Chandradhar. 1960 A Critical Survey of Indian Philosophy, Motilal Banarasidass
- Radhakrishnan. S. 1958 Indian Philosophy, George Allen and Unwin Ltd, Vol 2

12 Śaṅkara says here that even if a hundred sruti passages were to say that fire is cold and non-luminous, they would not gain the status of being a pramāṇa. They would not be valid. Because, no means of knowledge can contradict what can be known by another means of knowledge